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[Diagnostics] Manuscript ID: diagnostics-2681155 - Submission Received

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Dear Professor Graña,

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Journal name: Diagnostics

Manuscript ID: diagnostics-2681155

Type of manuscript: Article

Title: A critical reading of "COVID-19 Prediction Using Black-Box Based Pearson Correlation Approach"

Authors: Manuel Graña *, Goizalde Badiola-Zabala, Guillermo Cano-Escalera

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